

The Factors Influencing the Adoption of the Mobile App Payments via Personal Care Apps in Telecommunication Sector of Sri Lanka

Prasad Nimantha Madusanka, U.H.¹, Dilina Herath²

¹ London Metropolitan University, 166-220 Holloway Road, London N7 8DB

² Dean of Business Management, Esoft Metro Campus, Colombo 3, Sri Lanka

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7713255

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7713255>

Abstract: The adoption of mobile app wallets for payments in Sri Lanka is slower than expected, with 65% of consumers not seeing any benefits in using them according to a study by the Federal Reserve Bank. This research aims to identify the key factors that contribute to this slow adoption. Traditional payment methods are still prevalent in Sri Lanka, but the telecommunication industry, being the largest industry in the service sector, requires a fast and easy medium for payments. Online methods are seen as more profitable due to the additional commission fees involved in conventional payments. Enabling a mobile app for payments may save costs and provide a seamless experience for users. Four main factors that could influence mobile app payment adoption have been identified and this research aims to confirm their impact.

Abbreviations: *IT:* Information Technology, *AML:* Anti-Money Laundering, *KYC:* Know-Your-Customer, *PLC:* Public Limited Company, *MPRI:* The Mobile Payment Readiness Index, *PIN:* Personal Identification Number, *NFC:* Near Field Communication

I. INTRODUCTION

The technological innovation has been the cause of the improvement of the economic performance in various business sectors in the global market and emerging economies in various parts of the world. Especially computerized processes and development of mobile computing devices advanced the pace of the economy with the convenience created among the consumers for the communication and transacting businesses.

In such a technologically disruptive environment nowadays businesses are adopting new technological means as channels to reach their consumers more efficiently to increase the awareness and profitability. The internet base services have been sufficiently providing that space of business to the many service providers from various sectors, however in the telecommunication sector providing service through a website was not sufficient enough, as their scope of business is targeted on handsets/cell phones which is currently undergoing a breakthrough in the past decade. As the lifestyle becomes more and more tightly scheduled consumers are more prone to get adopted to the devices that makes their day to day life convenient. Thus, consumers' behavior indicates a massive surge in the adoption of the smartphone devices. In the telecommunication sector, which had been a primary medium of communication in the past, internet based other messenger and

video chat services enabled the consumers to be more close and personal to their peers than it had been done in the past via telecommunication methods; such as texts and voice calls. Instead, the rapidly growing internet-based communication services has now becoming the trend in every smartphone user. In the past couple of years, the smartphone manufacturers have determined to improve the capabilities of these smartphones enabling a whole new dimension of businesses, such as One-Click Payments and NFC, with the introduction of mobile apps. The primary revenue in the telecommunication sector is based on the collections of the subscriptions and many telecom operators are aiming towards collecting their due payment from consumers using a mobile app, which in turn making the collections mechanism more fluid and prompt. However, the researcher has identified certain bottlenecks that may create an obstacle in the industry for the conversion of the consumers for this payment collection mechanism.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Although the implementation of mobile app transaction technologies continues to increase, still organizations finds it difficult to reap the complete benefit of using mobile app payment platforms-or have not experienced its full potential in action. As a result, the emerging economies experience hindrances in trade expansion. It seems to be only a limited number of business models are able to reap the maximum benefit of a mobile app. From the mere sight of it, one can determine the fact that the consumers are more using such mobile app platforms for entertainment purposes such as mobile games, movies, videos, music and other social networking initiatives. As the social networking continues to expand its reach, users are more likely to adopt to such a platform that can magnify the users reach instead of limited themselves to a telecommunication operator that provides only a limited amount of services.

Many firms that operate in the telecommunication industry, has already began to provide their services using mobile apps. However, many firms in the industry finds it difficult to have their consumers converted to the new platform, as their primary intention of using a mobile app is to have their subscribers to reach to them as a platform of communication and for requesting additional services instead of reaching the firms' call center of walking in to an outlet. Such services mainly include additional service activations, checking the credit balance in the telecom

products, requests additional data when required, and paying their subscription fee. During the initial probing in the matter the researcher has already identified there is a significant demand from the consumer's side for the user of a mobile app, mainly for making their subscription payments on time, as it may often lead to service interruption if not paid on the due date. However, it is confirmed the fact, that many users still do not make an effort to adopt to a mobile app platform for making payments, despite its advantages. Therefore, this research is thoroughly intended to identify the key variables that contributes to the adoption of Mobile App Payment options of the end user. This study is intended to make a significant contribution to the knowledge of the commercial bodies of the Mobile App industry or the commercial entities that involves Mobile App as their key payment receiving channel. Enterprises will benefit the outcomes of this study as to what it uncovers in terms of the key reasons that improves or impair the effectiveness of the Mobile App payment adoption of the users. Thus, it will provide enlightenment on which areas the businesses should concentrate for the enhancement when a Mobile App payment option is used, and which areas to be vigilant and conduct business as usual.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study is aimed at determining factors that influences a user's perspective and experience towards the adoption of mobile payment apps in the telecommunication sector, whilst cultivating the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). For research purposes the research has synthesized a set specific objectives as follows;

- To find the relationship between the App Downtimes and the Mobile App payment adoption.
- Find the relationship between the User Experience Design of the app and the Mobile App payment adoption.
- Find the relationship between the used Payment Method of the end user and the Mobile App payment adoption.
- Find the relationship between the "Payment Verification" process and the Mobile App payment adoption.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study is aimed at determining factors that influences a user's perspective and experience towards the adoption of mobile payment apps in the

A. Industry Overview

With the popularity of the smartphones, mobile apps industry transformed in to mobile gaming, social network and internet retailing. As described by Frierman (2011), 15,000 new apps are being released every week. In order for a business model in the mobile app industry to be successful, its platform owner should offer their flexible and consistent corporation to the app developer and managers as much as possible. This can be in the forms of the support provided to the stakeholders at the development level, mainly for the developers and maintaining a friendly and functional environment. Naturally, its developers' intent to maintain complete and an active community to improve

further development. This can make the developments easy and faster for the developers, as it would be more efficient for them to allocate the necessary resources, knowledge and practices for the process for a faster delivery of the required features, rather than having them waste away from the unclear documentation and cumbersome coding (Power,2012). One of the best examples for this is the methodology followed by the organizations like Apple Inc and Google, is their process of cultivating the ecosystems of libraries that consists of APIs (Application programming Interfaces), that can reduce the work involved during a creation of an application. These APIs greatly improves the programming of applications in the mobile industry and the business cases, by increasing the efficiency by simplifying difficult tasks of programming in the mobile interface and reduces the chances of bugs (Power, 2012). The mobile app industry faced a significant growth after the launch of the Apple's iPhone in 2007, potentially valuing \$100 billion by 2015 (Rakestraw et al, 2013).

B. Industry Forecasts.

In the year 2012, the mobile app industry estimated to be a \$17.5 billion business model worth worldwide. It was estimated a 92% increase per annum in the mobile app downloads, given the fact of the 7 billion app downloads hike in 2009 risen to 50 billion in 2012 (Floriceanu, 2010). As per the Statista (2020) it is indicated this pattern to be continued at an exponential trend; from \$97 billion in 2014 up to \$461 billion in 2019, further it is expected to grow high as \$935 billion in the year 2023. These figures indicate a massive opportunity for app developers and the business owners as the industry progresses in such a rapid growth. In addition, further studies estimated in 2012, off deck applications; the apps that are not approved by the mobile carriers, taken a nearly 50% of all revenues in the mobile app industry in 2012, and by 2009 it was risen to 60% of all revenues in the industry (Floriceanu, 2010). However, it was projected to be reduced to 23% of the revenues by the year of 2012. The intense competition in the mobile app business has increased so many flaws in the developments, resulting steep hikes in the failure rates in among mobile app businesses world-wide. In the Apple Appstore the top 10% popular apps take 80% of the all apps downloaded. As a result of this many mobile app developers now resorting to develop third party apps to increase their revenues (Floriceanu, 2010). In the United States alone the third-party app development has the highest demand in downloads hence resulting 98% of all development projects from the concept development, user design and coding. This was to be reduced to be 70% by the end of 2015. Analytics estimated the app maintenance, analytics and distribution of the apps and extension services generated 2% out of the industry revenue in 2010. However, this percentage was later estimated to increase up to nearly 30% by the year 2015 (Perez, 2011). At the moment third party app developers are flourishing in Western Europe and the United States. In addition, the emerging markets such as China and India have shown an immense potential in the mobile app industry (Perez, 2011). It was anticipated that the average price of mobile apps will decrease by 29%. Furthermore, the number of mobile app stores has increased from 8 to 38 in the year 2009 alone and was expected to be grow rapidly from 2012 and beyond. In addition, the methods of revenue generation has also changing. As an example, in the year 2009 advertising accounted only for 12% of the app revenues and it was expected to be doubled in the year 2012 (Floriceanu, 2010).

The researcher is fully convinced that as per the above scholars' affirmation of the potential of the Mobile App market, there is a significant potential lying for many businesses. However, it is the researcher's intention to identify whether this realm is an actual opportunity for a firm that operating in the telecommunication sector. It is the general norm that the telecom products turning obsolete, whilst the mobile app market surge in comparison. Further literature provided in this study will assist to further determine the actual applications and practical issues that could be an actual case.

C. Mobile App Users

The businesses that includes online financial services, are recognized as highly information-intensive industries, and it is often debated that a firm's performance in the customer satisfaction and loyalty in the market is solely depended on the customer's experience in the flow of the events with in the service delivery process (Chase and Dasu 2001). Also, past researches revealed that the sequence of events and peak experiences in a service delivery process affect customer satisfaction. In any enterprise that customer service plays an integral part, the processual and experiential aspects of the services are recognized as a pivotal factor (Edvardsson et al., 2005).

The customer experience, which is a combination of customer's emotional, social, cognitive and physical response towards a company (Verhoef et al., 2009) is the key to gain the competitive advantage for the businesses operated in the service sector proximity (Meyer and Schwager, 2007).

D. System Downtimes

System downtimes can be common to any service that consists of IT, however when the customer finds the absence of the service during his requirement of the service, he may approach competitors after the system downtimes. This is mainly due to the degree of damage in customer satisfaction at the time of the necessity from the customer point of view. This will lead users to prevent from using the same platform again in future, making customer losses. System Downtime is a mandatory process that the developers often carry out during the app upgrades and internal service maintenance; hence unlike "System Errors" they are intentional and controllable. Putting controls in place to reduce such upgrade times can reduce the System Downtimes, that reduces the times of denial of services during downtime durations.

However other scholars have shown that the design of service delivery mechanism to facilitate swift in higher performances in user journey performance (Schmenner 2004; Schmenner and Swink 1998). The creation of user experiences can be intentionally done when the service provider uses services as the stage and the goods as props, to engage customers, in a way that creates a memorable event (Pine and Gilmore 1999). The user experience is a combination of logically necessary consequences of cumulative customer perceptions created during interactions with a product or service (Pullman and Gross 2004). A study of Chase and Dasu (2001) shows that the use of behavioral science is enhancing customer experience; and by engineering customer experience with the proper management of systematic clues that embody the customer's experiences with service systems can trigger their

emotions (Berry et al, 2006). Furthermore, a study done by Rodgers et al (2005) revealed; that the users participated were influenced by the perception of the purchase/payment experience.

By the year of 2010 the mobile app industry turned increasingly saturated with lifestyle apps and numerous utilitarian. A survey conducted by Nielsen (2010), revealed specific types of mobile apps that have greater consumer demand. In a situation where the demand is high the damage that the mobile app service can occur increases with the denial of the service due to system downtime. The businesses that often rely on a mobile app payment system which generates revenue, the cost of failed online transactions can be significant: a single hour of a downtime can cause thousands of dollars in lost for the retailer. The true cost of downtimes however can be much higher due to dissatisfied or lost customers, damage to the reputation of the company, and impacts on company stock prices by the lost employee productivity.

Although the scholars point out the system downtime is an instrument that hinders the consumer user journey, the researcher points out a doubt whether there are significant amount of downtimes that actually intervenes during the user journey of the consumers, hence this matter is planned to be tested to determine.

E. System Errors and Manifestation of Failure

The "System Errors" unlike "System Downtimes" are not intentional, yet it has the same effect towards the user during mobile app payments. They are often difficult to control; however, it is possible to implement detection mechanism and trend forecasts to predict these unexpected errors.

As per Pertet & Narasimhan (2005), the definition of the failures or the manifestation of the failure has direct correlation with the user-visible effects of a failure. Although there are multiple underlying causes when it comes to the Web applications and Mobile applications, they are varied in their manifestation, hence they can be typically categorized under the following broad areas (Pertet & Narasimhan, 2005):

- Site/Service unavailability (Partial or entire): The "Request Time-outs"; that are the user's request times out that creates an error to the user notifying "404 file not found". This is usually a due to network congestion, denial of service attacks or server crashes and hangs.

- System exceptions and access violations: Access Violations and System exceptions: When there is a system exception is thrown the executing process is terminated abruptly more often. In addition, the error messages that receive may vary depending on the error handling in the crashed application. For an example: the system may set to indicate a detailed access violation message included with addresses ad numbers or sometimes nothing at all.

- Incorrect results: There could be instances where the executing process does not terminate, instead it may just return erroneous results. As an example, the bank pages, wrong pages or wrong items could be returned when the user tried to access. As there are no exceptions thrown, or triggers raised usually these failures are only discovered when a customer complaint.

- Data corruption and loss: When the users are unable to access the data from the previously functioning computer system; where it may have experienced an accidental data erasure. Corruptions are usually occurred by a boundary

overwrite in the memory and are considered the most difficult to diagnose. Usually most of the time developers chase after the effect of the memory corruptions first, rather than the cause of the problem. Generally, the characteristics of a data corruption may contain corrupt data or random-access violations.

- **Slowness in Performance:** System slowness could be a result of many reasons such as process hangs, service overload, resource exhaustion, deadlocks and network congestion.

F. Mobile App Speed

A study published by Solis (2018) has determined that majority of the users' primary intention of using smartphones is to find and purchase items. They use smartphones to learn, analyze and filter choices to draw informed decisions. This process demands speed; and entirely depended on the speed of the mobile, which often considered never fast enough for the users. As the speed increases the users are empowered not entitled, hence they reach for the nearest device that can be accessible fast.

As per a research done by Google (Kleinberg, 2018), the participants from US, UK and Australia, Japan and Germany, revealed the following opinions they are having towards smartphones.

- 1). Productive and Efficient - 73%
- 2). Confident and Prepared – 54%
- 3). Able to make better decisions – 55%

This is evident that the speed of the Mobile App has a direct impact for the user journey and in avertedly influences the mobile app payment adoption.

G. User Design of the Mobile App

There are multiple researches from both scholars and practitioners have gained considerable interest on the user experience. These researches are generally focused on the factors that affect the user's interaction and experience of the system or process of the product (Partala & Saari, 2015).

Chen's UX assessment model has been adopted in (Paula 2014). Brasil 9+ is a mobile application for BlackBerry 10 that offers a service to add the ninth digit to the left of the current mobile numbers. The UX assessment was conducted to identify the main criteria that influence the experience of Brasil 9+. The details of UX assessment were shown in Table 1. Based on the users' feedback, they were uncomfortable to leave the application running on the background while doing another task.

Many scholars such as Arvidsson and Markendahl (2014), Carton and Hedman (2013), Hedman (2012), followed by their studies predicted that soon we will be experiencing a cashless society.

Holzer and Ondrus (2009) suggests; based on their study on the concepts "One-Integrated-Portal" and "One-Click-Purchase"; which consists of end-to-end solutions for user registrations, browsing and purchases make a difference in consumption levels, and that they can make the end user experience much better. However, Holzer and Ondrus (2009) do not discuss about the user interface or recommended guidelines for Mobile App design. Therefore, these options and their effects are planned to be discussed during this research.

Payments are intensely engraved in our daily life, and day-in day-out people carry various payments in various contexts with different methods. Evans and Schmalensee (2005)

describes how the financial transactions between people and organizations have been evolved from Cash and Cheques, which were the most common exchange means for financial transactions and purchases in 1900s, until the arrival of the Payment Cards, commonly known as Credit or Debit cards by the later part of the 1900s. Beyond the year 2000 this has further developed to mobile phones and its capabilities enhanced as payment devices.

H. Payment Methods Used

This is understood as more convenient the transaction methods become, faster it becomes for the consumer to quench their requirements which involves paying a sum. Nowadays, Debit and Credit cards are the still widely used payment methods. Although there is a considerable increase in trends have been noticed; the usage of E-wallets is much preferred over Payment Card options in certain situations. This study is planned to find out if there is a significant influence in payment option used in a Personal Mobile Care mobile app for payments.

H.1 Credit Cards:

With the developing technology, the need for alternative payment tools to meet the ever-increasing needs of individuals has led to the emergence of credit card payment systems by improving payment instruments. Payment instruments are classified mainly under four main groups. These are respectively; credit cards, spending cards, bank cards, and store cards (Kaya, 2009: 1).

A credit card is a payment instrument which enables customers to buy goods and services and to use cash credits within the determined credit limits allocated to the customers. Despite it doesn't have the similar features of the modern credit card, the first credit card was introduced in the nineteenth century. In 1894, the first credit card in the history was issued by the Hotel Letter Credit Company based in US and in course of time it has been used to control various oil companies and stores to check customer accounts. In 1968, the first credit card was released to the market in Turkey which was called as the "Dinners Clubs". However, the use of credit cards remained limited due to the high inflation and the crisis resulting from interest rates at that time. But; payment instruments have become widespread in Turkey as well as all around the world in the 1990s as a result of the positive developments in the global financial markets. (Aysan and Müslim, 2006).

H.2 Debit Cards:

On the other hand, this stream of research has rarely touched upon debit cards. The only existing evidence on whether debit cards incur higher spending than cash comes from a field experiment on charitable giving. As per Soetevent (2011), conditional on choosing to donate money using debit cards can lead to higher amounts of donations compared to cash base mediums. However, there are only 9% of the debit card treatments chosen to be approached by the households, compared to 67% in the cash treatments. This difference is due to the fact that the households are choosing to donate from the loose change they have available, or due to other household characteristics. However, the propensity score matching estimator indicates that the households with the same characteristics have a tendency to donate using more debit cards

than cash but controlling for cash-on-hand constraints is not possible in this setting.

Another major factor involving Debit/Credit cards are that certain platforms may not allowed to save the card to the platform used. This is due to certain regulations applied in each sector related to the user data privacy protection. Due to this most card holders have to insert the card data every time they make a payment. This may drastically impact on the users' usability of the mobile app payment platforms as it creates an inconvenience.

H.3 E-Wallet:

As described by Kemp (2013), the new market initiatives such as mobile operators, e-card schemes, service integrators and device suppliers are rigorously advancing in the development of the three chains of the payments, retail, mobile and technology industries, which are the objects of the most significant investments in the smartphone industry.

As per Simplot-Ryl, Traoré, & Everaere (2012), the number of E-commerce transactions has shown a considerable increase for the past several years. The Mobile Payment Readiness Index (MPRI) monitors the readiness for mobile payments in 34 countries that represent 85% collectively in the household consumption globally; that indicates the market has reached the proximity of the inflection point. At this point the mobile devices count for a considerable share of the payment mix (Mastercard, 2012; Hernandez, 2014). The increasing trend of smartphone users has encouraged the merchants and business owners to communicate with their consumers using their mobile devices itself by sending new product lists, promos, provide coupons and also facilitate payments and purchasing options (Yang et al., 2012). In addition, mobile wallet mechanisms enable functions that allow users to manage receiving information from merchants and business owners and to compare the product information and prices between retailer and different products.

The mobile wallets allow customer to turn their smartphones in a channel where they can make payments and commit purchases of services and goods. In order to use the smartphones as mobile wallets the consumers would have to download the service provider's mobile wallet app and enter their debit/credit card information. After this procedure is completed the consumers can proceed to make payments by simply using their smartphones by scanning them on the service providers NFC readers or QR Code Readers. A mobile wallet is considered a much more advanced and a fluent application that comprise of options such as mobile transactions, loyalty cards, membership cards and stores sensitive and personal information such as credit card information and passport details, PIN codes, booking details, online shopping accounts, social profiles and insurance policies that can be encrypted or password protected (Caldwell, 2012). In addition, mobile app wallets can support various types of transactions such as consumer-to-business, consumer-to-consumer, consumer-to-online, and consumer-to-machines; for example, payment over a parking ticket machine. Furthermore, the mobile money wallets provide greater flexibility to consumers during transactions at the point of the purchase with smartphones due to the portability and cashless nature. Such functionalities of the mobile app wallets are not solely providing convenience to the consumer but also provide the marketers a wide array of possibilities to enhance their marketing capabilities, particularly the wealth of intelligence about the

consumers shopping behavior. Such intelligence could provide a greater competitive advantage to enhance the consumer shopping experience, in another word it enables the markets to develop a close relationship with their consumers.

The researcher as drilled down multiple areas of the payment methods used during this research to justify if there are any relation towards the payment adoption of mobile apps. The researcher clearly convinced the fact that there is significant relation between the recurrent use of any payment method, and its very nature of usability for conducting payments. Hence, the user will be seeking if any tendencies of consumer to prefer one payment method over the other, when used a mobile app for the payments.

I. Verification Process

Since the year 2015 there has been continuous regulatory enforcements, pressuring the mobile and online money markets regarding the Anti-Money-Laundering (AML). In order to maintain the compliance with the AML many governments maintain standard policies and imposes large profile fines and continuously maintaining surveillances and investigations. As a result, the Know Your Customer (KYC) in another word the standard verification process and various sanctions requirements continues to be the key focus area for firms and the management regulatory in order to follow the appropriate compliance procedures to meet the regulatory demands. Especially the companies that operate globally is required to be demonstrating a compliance framework robustly in order to ensure the management of the oversight in each territory and that the AML requirements are appropriately adhered in both local and global level. Therefore, the verification procedure during payments in Mobile Applications remained to be a mandatory procedure.

However, according to Frei (2006), by reducing the variability in the service delivery process, the efficiency can be increased and customer service and can expect higher performance in the service delivery and customer experience. The standard verification process that are implemented during payments in mobile app platform can increase additional tasks a user has to perform to fulfill his payment requirement. As an example, a new payment verification process that is newly introduced to a Mobile App during payments, may cause a sudden volatility in the volumes of the money flow, and may cause serious financial sacrifices in the long run. This process flow in the mobile app payment procedure is required to be closely analyzed during this research in terms of the user experience, whether it is creating any drivers of satisfaction to increase or decrease the mobile app payment adoption.

The European Central Bank, concentrates on the most innovative payment methods currently used based on the credit and debit cards (Kokkola, 2010). The major reason for this is the fact that they are initially designed to use on face-to-face transactions that are conducted in physical premises of the merchants. However nowadays the cards are used for remote transactions at an increasing rate, followed by the trends of mobile phones and web-based internet purchases (Kokkola, 2010). However, as the cards are design for physical usage, the physical existence of the user is taken as the primary verification, the remote usage of the cards where the card is considered "not present", the risk of fraud is phenomenally high, and European Central Bank has determined this trend based on the increasing online payment trends. As a result, all the card

based transactions are instructed to be devised in more advance and newer ways to increase security and carry out a remote authentication and an authorization mechanism (Kokkola, 2010).

The researcher is intended to determine in this research whether there is significant impact to the consumer bases that uses mobile app payment platform, while maintaining the aforesaid security measures. The research is equipped to cover many aspects in the payment verification process; from the user’s willingness to provide all the necessary verifications irrespectively of the time spent, to the point where they are inclined to provide only one-time verification to avoid the repetition of using the same card and spending an extended time during future payments.

IV. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Is there a relationship between the App Downtimes and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector?
2. Is there a relationship between the User Experience Design of the app and Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector?
3. Is there a relationship between the used Payment Method used by the end user and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector?
4. Is there a relationship between the “Payment Verification” process and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector?

V. CONCEPTUAL DEVELOPMENT

A. Hypothesis

1.

H0- There is no relationship between the App Downtimes and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector.

H1- There is a relationship between the App Downtimes and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector.

2.

H0- There is no relationship between the User Experience Design of the app and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector.

H1- There is a relationship between the User Experience Design of the app and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector.

3.

H0- There is no relationship between the used Payment Method used by the end user and Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector.

H1- There is a relationship between the used Payment Method used by the end user and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector

4.

H0- There is no relationship between the “Payment Verification” process and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector.

H1- There is a relationship between the “Payment Verification” process and the Mobile App payment adoption in Telecommunication sector. For Author/s of Only One Affiliation (Heading 3): To change the default, adjust the template as follows.

VI. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Identifying the factors behind the increased or decreased trends in the payment adoption of the personal care app can generate a theory on the solution of the problem. However, the theory is the collection of interrelated variables that showcases a systematic view of the phenomena by specifying the relation among those variables (Kerlinger, 1979, cited in Creswell, 2003, p.120).

The figure below represents the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable in this study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

VII. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Theoretical Stance

The type of research used for this study is quantitative and descriptive in nature. The research philosophy used for this study is positivism, which is an objective stance depended on facts and figures and both primary and secondary quantitative data. The research approach of this study is followed by the inductive approach, which intended to find answers to the questions that are formulated in the early stages of the study. Below Research Onion of Saunders et al (2009) depicts in a nutshell. The research questions will be addressed by a mixed method study which uses user engagement statistics data collected by Dialog Axiata PLC, a company operated in the telecommunication industry in Sri Lanka. The research design is intended provide the ultimatum of the realized answers to the research question.

Figure 1: Research Onion (Saunders et al, 2009).

The researcher planned the deduction procedure to be operationalized, while following the principles of reductionism, enabling the facts to be measured in a quantitative manner with less errors. To test this, I have carried out the Cronbach Alpha testing using the SPSS tool.

B. Validity

The researcher placed controls to maintain the validity of the research, as control groups and participant groups may prone to external influences equally. During the survey of the individuals that are closely associated to the business of Dialog Axiata PLC and management, they were taken to a more controlled environment. Furthermore, the data received/recorded are made sure to be live and accurate as its being done with Dialog Axiata and the customers are selected from Dialog Axiata Data base. Data collected from valid samples with valid questions to the objectives.

C. Constraints & Ethics

C.1 Constraints.

The major constraints experienced during this study is the time constraints. Based on the other demands to be met in day to day life, it was recognized the proper management of required energy and time capacity. In order to mitigate this, the research associated with the research assistants. More time was taken when acquiring the questionnaires, hence continuous follow ups was done with the participants, to obtain the responds.

C.2 Ethical Considerations.

Participants' rights: Prior to the collection of data participants' consent was obtained. Furthermore, without causing any harm still the participants' rights were preserved to withdraw the application if the participants felt or to allowed them to not answer or participate in certain questionnaires if they felt not wanting to answer. Thus, once access has been granted

the goal of the research objectives will be maintained (Zikmund 2000).

Objectivity: During the data collection procedure the researcher aimed to avoid any exercise of subjective selections of data. In return this was also influenced the aforementioned reliability and validity. The fabrication of such data is an unethical course of action and without objectively collected data the accuracy of the analysis be impaired; therefore, adherence was made sure in every step of the data collection to the data representation. (Saunders et al, 2009).

Confidentiality: During the survey procedure of the internal parties of the selected organizations the anonymity was maintained by the researcher, and at the time of obtaining secondary information from data sources, if promised the confidentiality was maintained, especially related to the names, addresses and personal information (Economic and Social Data Service 2007).

Anonymity: Having certain information with in the reports could have led to revealing the identity of individuals or the organizations. Therefore, the quantitative data was anonymized by aggregating straightforward variables by the researcher (Saunders et al, 2009). As described by Easterby-Smith et al. (2008), during this research as it progresses the factors revealed were not discussed with the participants nor shared previous participants' thoughts on the same research questionnaire with the current participant, this has ensured the process not bring any harm by the researcher.

Reactivity: In this research, the researcher if any contact was made with the participants of the questionnaire, the boundaries were maintained with the participants, especially when the participant reacted to his/her personal matters such as phone calls during the observation process or when reacted to the research strategy applied. The objective of this was to maintain the relationship between the researcher and the participant (Bryman 1988:112).

D. Data Collection Method & Tools

To achieve the objectives of this research both primary and secondary data was utilized to provide insights on the findings. Primary data was collected from questionnaires from the sample base selected. A research assistance was associated for the administration of the questionnaire. During this process household individuals, corporate executives, professionals, and company agents, who can be included in the sample base, were requested to participate in the questionnaire. In the end these data were combined with the data received from the secondary data resources such as: websites, books, journal articles and historical data available from Dialog Axiata PLC, and the reports were analyzed to identify trends and if there are any popularities based on each stratum. The appropriate approval process and the data security protocols were followed for the data collection. The variables were applied in a quantitative method as forms of numbers with specific measurements and was put into analysis. The ultimatum of the findings was brought into the study as graphs and charts in visual forms.

E. Research Timeframe

This research was planned for a duration of 6 months starting from the first week of August, 2019 and elapsed until 31st of January, 2020. As shown in the Gantt chart in the figure 3 (Appendix 1), the action items 1 and the 2, the identification of the research topic and formulating the research questions, design, methodology and strategy has been already completed and the remaining data analysis completed and the final report submission is the final task that is remaining.

VIII. DATA ANALYSIS

For this research, the factor of System Downtime was measured by the perceptions of the App Downtimes that often occurs in the app development, the Speed of the app and the Stability. Also, the Time to take for a Payment to Update and the System Errors that pop-up when using the app, were expected to indicate the impact of a user’s preference to use Mobile app for Payment.

The User-Design of the app, was measured by the User-Interface used in the app, which was the environment of the app that makes the first impression for a user and that creates the interest towards usability. Number of Click-times providing during the usage, was also taken as a measure to find to get an understanding of the time taken for a user to complete payment, and if the users are having any opinion towards it when making a mobile app for payments. Further, the level of Access given to the Payment Feature, and its visibility and easiness to find during an urgent payment is also measured with the Ease of Use and the graphical/colour appearance of the app.

The level of impact of the Payment Methods Used by the app, was also intended to measure as; based on the convenience and preferences of the users there were implications of influence for mobile payment adoption. Hence it was measured by the perception of the users on the payment methods such as Credit/Debit Card, EzCash, Cash, Genie E-wallet, and Internet Payment. Also, it is intended to find whether users have a tendency for Cash only payment, which will deny the use of a mobile app for payments.

The verification process is measured by the user’s preferences towards the Multiple Verifications during a payment, alternative Secondary Verification option, to allowing to save the Payment Credential as a one-time option, Privacy, not having Verifications.

The measurement of the Payment Adoption is the level of agreement shown by the participants; that if they think their adaptation for a mobile payment platform has any influence on the aforesaid factors by any means.

A. Introduction

Data was collected from 378 users representing the 220,333 consistent mobile app payee base, using a Likert scale questionnaire. This effort was intended to gain insight of the

users’ perception and preferences during payment adoption or the key drivers, or if the provided factors had any effect at all for their decision to choose a mobile app platform for payments in the telecommunication sector.

The descriptive qualitative data output and the quantitative statistical data output were derived by analyzing the survey data using the SPSS Statistics tool of IBM.

B. Descriptive Statistics

As per the statistics, during the identification of the significance of the “Payment Methods Used” is the highest significant factor with the highest mean value which is 2.68. The next highest significance variable was the “Verification Process” with a mean value of 2.60. The “System Downtimes” was the following highest variable with a mean value of 2.2507 and lastly the “User Experience Design” variable was with the insignificant level of a mean value of 1.9058.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
System_Downtimes	375	1.00	5.00	2.2507	.75707
User_Experience_Design	378	1.00	4.00	1.9058	.56420
The_Payment_Method_Used	372	1.00	4.20	2.6887	.66209
Verification_Process	375	1.20	4.20	2.6005	.65071
Valid N (listwise)	366				

C. Correlation Test

		App_Downtimes	User_Experience_Design	The_Payment_Method_Used	Verification_Process	App_Adoption
System_Downtimes	Pearson	1	.472**	.323**	.279**	-.094
	Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.069
	N	375	375	369	372	375
User_Experience_Design	Pearson	.472**	1	.263**	.477**	-.072
	Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.162
	N	375	378	372	375	378
The_Payment_Method_Used	Pearson	.323**	.263**	1	.517**	-.049
	Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.346
	N	369	372	372	369	372
Verification_Process	Pearson	.279**	.477**	.517**	1	-.045
	Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.385
	N	372	375	369	375	375
App_Adoption	Pearson	-.094	-.072	-.049	-.045	1
	Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.069	.162	.346	.385	
	N	375	378	372	375	378

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation analysis done on the Payment Adoption and the System Downtime, the result is -0.094 which indicates that there is a low negative relationship between Payment Adoption and the System Downtime.

The correlation analysis done on the Payment Adoption and the User Experience Design, the result is -0.072 which indicates that there is a low negative relationship between the Payment Adoption and the User Experience Design.

Based on the correlation analysis done on the Payment Adoption and the Payment Methods Used, the result is -0.049 which indicates that there is a low negative relationship between the Payment Adoption and the Payment Methods Used.

As per the correlation analysis done on the Payment Adoption and the Verification Process, the result is -0.405 which indicates that there is a low negative relationship between the Payment Adoption and the Verification Process.

D. Hypothesis Test

C.1 Hypothesis test for System Downtime

The value of the Chi-Square of the payment adoption and the system downtime is 0.673 which is above than the asymptomatic significance of 0.05, which shows there is no significant relationship between of the payment adoption and the system downtime at 95% confidence level. Therefore, H0 cannot be rejected.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	58.423 ^a	64	.673
Likelihood Ratio	66.269	64	.399
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.306	1	.069
N of Valid Cases	375		

a. 62 cells (72.9%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

C.2 Hypothesis test for User Experience Design

The value of the Chi-Square of the payment adoption and the User Experience Design is 0.878 which is above than the asymptomatic significance of 0.05, which shows there is no significant relationship between of the payment adoption and the system downtime at 95% confidence level. Therefore, H0 cannot be rejected

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	36.893 ^a	48	.878
Likelihood Ratio	40.848	48	.758
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.959	1	.162
N of Valid Cases	378		

a. 39 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

C.3 Hypothesis test for the Payment Methods Used

The value of the Chi-Square of the payment adoption and the Payment Methods Used is 0.609 which is above than the asymptomatic significance of 0.05, which shows there is no significant relationship between of the payment adoption and the system downtime at 95% confidence level. Therefore, H0 cannot be rejected.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	56.368 ^a	60	.609
Likelihood Ratio	58.838	60	.518
Linear-by-Linear Association	.889	1	.346
N of Valid Cases	372		

a. 54 cells (67.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

C.4 Hypothesis test for the Verification Process

The value of the Chi-Square of the payment adoption and the Verification Process is 0.698 which is above than the asymptomatic significance of 0.05, which shows there is no significant relationship between of the payment adoption and the system downtime at 95% confidence level. Therefore, H0 cannot be rejected.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	54.031 ^a	60	.692
Likelihood Ratio	57.894	60	.553
Linear-by-Linear Association	.758	1	.384
N of Valid Cases	375		

a. 56 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

Based on the above results of the hypothesis testing it was concluded that all the H0 hypothesis were accepted and confirmed that there is no actual correlation between the payment adoption and the tested independent variables.

E. Reliability Test

During the Cronbach-alpha test conducted using the IBM SPSS software it is recognized that the Alpha value as 0.825, whereas the reliability coefficient is considered as 0.70 and above. Thus, it is concluded that the data collected during this survey can be reliable.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.825	21

I. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

As stated at the beginning of this paper, this study is intended to obtain a broader understanding about the determinants that can potentially influence the users for the adoption of Mobile Apps for online payments. This research further focused on the factors that can affect the user's preferences based on their experience, appearance and willingness to use as a method in the industry application.

Furthermore, the end results will be cross referenced back to the academic literature in order to identify if the facts presented in the context were in accordance for the actual occurrences in the nature revealed during the assessment of data. And if disagreed-any alterations or recommendations to be made for the industry norm, with in the Mobile App technology application in the Telecommunication Sector in Sri Lanka. The main factors that were identified for the testing were based on the instances where the industry has identified, and the internal information revealed by user feedbacks.

A. A summary of the research & key findings

This thesis has assessed the findings of the results of a survey carried out by the users in the telecommunication sector, who has already possessed the firsthand experience in the use of Mobile App for payments. As a predominant service provider of the industry Dialog Axiata PLC still find it difficult to achieve a significant adoption of the users.

The majority of the consumers are identified as they are using traditional payment methods such as visiting an outlet and making payments for the services of the organization. Based on the literature found, the factors that were speculated as they can be influential for the decrease/increase of the mobile app payment adoption, such as: System Downtimes, User Experience Design, Payment Methods Used and Verifications; seems to show no significant correlation as revealed during the testing of data. Therefore, the researcher has revisited and made an inquiry with the relevant business owners of the MyDialog App, and determined the underlined causes that may have resulted such a circumstance.

A.1 Research Question 1 - What is the relationship between the System downtimes and the Mobile payment adoption.

The system downtimes were speculated at the inception of the research, as an enforcer that can disrupt the user journey and create dislike towards the adoption of the mobile app. And the research was intended to identify if there are any relationship towards the payment adoption. However, the majority of the participants did not find it a significant impact for their decision, or in their preference in the experience. However, still a number of participant made it clear how the system downtimes affected their usage of the mobile app as a payment platform, still indicating a subtle relationship between the System Downtimes and the Mobile Payment Adoption. This can be considered as an opportunity to the organization to make improvements to reduce the number of audience by better planning and controlling the aspects of the system downtimes.

Justification for the absence of the significant relationship:

Based on the research results above, the researcher had convened the business owners to observe the practical side in this scenario .The researcher is also being employed under the same business owners the information is provided, as that the firm is already deploying the system downtime notifications after the midnight, and the intentional downtimes are carried out only after 1.00AM of the day, where the mobile app having a minimum usage of 6000 users per 30 minutes, where as there are 250,000 users are active during a usual business day (Appendix 3)

A.2 Research Question 2 - What is the relationship between the User Experience and Design and the Mobile payment adoption.

It was the understanding prior this research that there can be affects created via the User Experience and Design of the app, during payment adoption process a user. However, the data collected indicated that there is no such significant influence made to the participant who used the app. As quoted in the literature; although Holzer and Ondrus (2009) described the direct correlation of the performances of a product and how it can be affected by the end user experience/interface, the participants did not indicate it as a major factor. Hence, the above question was answered as there were not subjective relationship.

Justification for the absence of the significant relationship:

Again, the researcher has convened the business owners to justify this and carried out a "Funnel Analysis" of the user journey to determine if there are any flaws in the user journey. The researcher found out that the app analytics indicate that there are 98% of organic users are completing their journeys under actual conditions (Appendix 4).

A.3 Research Question 3 - What is the relationship between Payment Methods Used and the Mobile payment adoption.

In the literature review, although it was discussed that there was a significance influence on the users when it comes to the different payment methods and options, based on their medium and ease of used. Therefore, it was expected at the beginning of the research that there could be a relationship with the varying

payment methods used by the users against the adoption of the mobile payment. However, the survey data revealed that there was no significant impact on this.

Justification for the absence of the significant relationship:

Based on the data analysis and the feedback of the business owners, the researcher has determined the fact that the in the practical business condition the business owners only expecting the users who have are regularly using Card type, and other payment methods that are compatible with the standard mobile app payment platforms. The business owners pointed out the fact that there is a correlation between the “owning a smartphone” vs “Possessing a debit/credit card/ E-waller etc” is and counted as the potential base and the penetration percentage is 76% which is an above average achievement for any mobile app penetration in any sectors in Sri Lanka (Appendix 5). As the sample base is also consisted of 100% ordinary Dialog MyDialog App users, the inability of rejecting the H0 is understood.

A.4 Research Question 4 - What is the relationship between Verification Process and the Mobile payment adoption.

As discussed in the literature review, the verification process and the number of steps could increase or decrease the user perception on their willingness to use a mobile platform. However, based on the research data based on the survey it is confirmed that still this variable does not play a significant influence towards the users in their adoption for mobile app payment platform.

Justification for the absence of the significant relationship:

The researcher has carried out further discussions with the business owners and referred to the previous NPS data where the users have expressed their comments on the various aspects of the MyDialog App platform and its payment experience aspect. For the analyses the researcher has referred the data related to the months; October 2019 and November 2019. The analysis covered only the Detractors and the Passive voters and disregarded the Promoters. Out of 100% of a collection of Detractors and Passive voters there were only 1% identified as they had concerns on the payment experience of the mobile app, in each respective month (Appendix). For the month of November 2019 there were 1% out of 3,580. Given the fact that in the month November 2019 there were 1.1Mn+ users active (Appendix 7), the 1% counted out of a base of consumers of 3,580, the researcher determined that the selected sample base would have not represented the entirety's perception or if did it may have indicated a negligible amount under the statistical scope.

B. Limitations of the Research

B.1 Formulation of the research objectives:

The first challenge that the researcher encountered during this study was the formulation of the research objectives. As this is a subject that is found as not too often researched in terms of academic perspective, practical business issues found in the subject matter was much greater. Due to this the risk of making the objectives too broaden was much higher, making it difficult to research under controlled conditions.

B.2 Sample Size:

The particular subject being research is a matter that applied for a large population, as the research is being carried out in the Telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka. Therefore, the risk of reducing the accuracy was a huge concern. However, further limitations were encountered if planned to target a larger sample size, making the research process extended than the anticipated period. To mitigate this matter, the on Krejcie and Morgen (1970) sampling method was used to select a sufficiently accurate number of base for the data collection. This process was also put through a stratified sampling process as mentioned in 3.2 Sampling Framework and Generalizability.

B.3 Data Collection Method and Mechanism:

As the researcher is not a person who possess extensive experience in primary data collection, the data collection mechanism carried out could be prone to be flawed. Continuous interaction with experienced research personals were mandatory in the process to reduce any risk that may result an influence for an inadequate research outcome.

B.4 Lack of previous studies in the subject of research:

During the study it was recognized that are no sufficient literature available, in the academic binocular, related to specific technical aspects on mobile app payment adoption, specifically on aspects such as Verification Process, App Error and Consumer perception. The major reason for this can be the novelty of the technology and the lack of application and adoption of the subject in the contemporary as an academic perspective in narrow sector such as the telecommunication sector. However, they are rather taken as more practical application point of view, project assessments. Furthermore, the mobile app adaptation in the telecommunication industry has been a recent phenomenon. The researcher came to a realization where the sector is dire need of further research to increase the transparency of the phenomenon that are only exclusive for the telecommunication sector in Sri Lanka.

B.5 Research Scope Discussion:

Furthermore, during the interpretation of the various areas under each determinant and arranging them as facets to be prompt to the survey responded, one of the major challenge of the researcher was to present the questionnaire in a more comprehensible manner, as certain technical aspect may not be familiar to the users, however still it is mandatory to ask to obtain the relevant data for the expected research criteria. To reduce the impact of this, the questionnaire was edited and put through several experienced research assistants.

Furthermore, the researcher does not possess extensive research knowledge on the area, as well as he is not an experienced scholar in comprehensive research. Therefore, the depth of the discussion in this research paper may prone to compromise in various levels in comparison to the experienced scholars.

C. Reflection of the Research Process

When the researcher started the research, he was also working fulltime for a company in the telecommunication industry. The researcher was inspired to research on this subject due to the potential recognized as a professional in the Mobile App payment business. Although it's a convenient mode of

transaction, fast and trustworthy, still it was recognized with challenges during the adoption of the users.

During the research the researcher started reading related articles, research papers regarding the subject and it convinced the researcher on the areas and the future benefit that could gain from the knowledge that the research would generate in the process. Although as mentioned in the limitations the researcher found that there was no extensive academic study hence intended to peruse in this area, as it could provide me intellectual advantages in terms of the career.

This research process has enabled the researcher to look at things in an analytics point of view, and to listen to reasons impartially. The researcher gained the ability to maintain the academic discipline by respecting the research knowledge, people involved, methods followed and the ethical standard this research has demanded to be trained of. Especially it is noted the knowledge acquired in the SPSS in the data analysis has been fine experience to the researcher and can happily convey that it would even be able to use it in the professional environment.

Although the researcher gained lots of personal achievements from this research, it was thoroughly convinced that, this research could have been more applied with advanced research set-up and taken care of. Therefore, it's the researcher's firm believe that this research has lot to improve and realized there are areas than can be decisively improved if he is to conduct this research again. Such areas could be, increasing the sample size and accessing survey data faster from a large number of group of people that was selected by in this study, joining with couple of research assistance who possess more experience in the academic scope and by using more advance research and diverse testing mechanism in the process.

D. Recommendations

This research has observed and recognized the importance of the mobile app payment systems, and its benefits to the business and the end user. The details revealed in the study could fill the gap between the reasons as to what stopping the users from using a Selfcare Mobile App for payments online.

D.1 Recommendations on improvements for the System Downtimes during Mobile App payments.

The majority of the survey participants did not indicate their opinion, whether the System Downtimes are having a direct influence. Furthermore, the search also confirmed that there is no direct correlation of this variable towards the Payment Adoption of the users.

- **Planned Downtimes:** Despite it is still recommended to reduce the system downtimes as much as possible from the developer end and from the organization side. Or if mandatory to have them carried out at a time where the users are not at their best usage/Off Peak, preferably after midnight. The reason for this is still there were minor number of participants who have indicated their concern about the System Downtimes.

- **Unplanned Downtimes:** The researcher recommends the business owners to be always prepared for unplanned downtimes. Therefore, it is mandatory for the business owners to have their own create messages and

However, as indicated by the researcher there are no significant relationship between the system downtimes said and the mobile app payment adoptions. As justified in section 6.1.1, the researcher recommends carrying out further research on this matter, as under the practical conditions the users have not experience a significant amount of events and in return the sample base also did not reflect the same.

D.2 Recommendations on improving the User Experience Design of the app for the Mobile App payment adoption.

The majority of the participants have agreed, that they do not have a preference on any negative aspects of the User Experience Design of the app. Furthermore, the tests revealed that there is no significance relationship with this variable towards the payment adoption and as the results contradicted the scholar's views, the researcher recommends further studies on this variable to determine further effects of the user journey and impact towards the payment adoption in mobile app platform. Thus, further studies may reveal if any untouched factors within the User Experience Design of the app, that could have missed in this study or if any alternative factors that may still impact on the User Experience such as color pattern and psychological influence on the user.

D.3 Recommendations on improving the used Payment Method of the end user for the Mobile App payment adoption.

The majority of the users indicated that they do not have any significant issue on the payment methods used in the mobile app.

However, during the questionnaire, the majority of the users disagreed and strongly disagreed that they do not prefer using CASH or Online Banking options. This implies that there is still a requirement among the consumers towards the convenience in the payment making process that they are expecting for, which a mobile app can deliver. Furthermore, the tests suggested as there were no significance relation between this variable and the payment adoption, the further study in this area is recommended.

As the researcher pointed out at the justification for not having a relationship in the section A.3 it is recommended to continue further studies to determine whether this variable actually having a practical effect for the app users, and to discover other dimension of requirements regarding the payment methods used by the various users from a much larger sample group.

D.4 Recommendations on improving the "Payment Verification" process for the Mobile App payment adoption.

The majority of the users agreed that there were no concerns in the "Payment Verification" process used during their adoption to mobile apps that has payment option. Also, the research data is concluded the fact that there is no significant relationship with this variable and the payment adoption. However, it is identified in the testing, that there are majority of the users expressing their willingness to save their credentials at the first instances so that in their second and remaining instances they will be able to quickly complete the transaction. This will provide an idea towards the management to implement an option in the mobile app payment platform to save their payment credential to avoid having the users inserting their payment credential data over and over again in their frequent payments.

As per the researcher's justification for not having a relationship in the section A.4, the researcher recommends further study regarding this particular variable to identify its actual impact for the particular business peer group.

E. Recommendation for Further Study

Conclusively, the research confirmed that there is no statistical relationship between the variables proposed with the dependent variable, despite they indicated a subtle rational at each questionnaire level. As mentioned in the limitation of the research, the lack of the literature and research on this subject matter of payment adoption under exclusive environment such as telecommunication sector, may have created a barrier in identifying the factors in the initial study of this research topic. Although the existing study points out the said four variables as the most prominent factors for the payment adoption, the actual condition in the business appeared to be different and varied based on each research aspect of the technology, and after the consideration of the feedback received from the business owners of Dialog Axiata PLC during the revisit of the research questions by the researcher (Section A.1, A.2, A.3, A.4). Therefore, the researcher proposes further study on the Telecommunication Sector in Sri Lanka to determine or further the scope of the suspected other variables

Ultimately, it is recommended that this subject and the research to be further researched, for the identification of the more predominant determinants that may have missed by the researcher and the past studies. The researcher would prefer to emphasize a revisit on the data collection procedure and the questionnaire settings and carry out a rigorous extended study on the matter to identify, as a secondary measure to affirm that there were no absolute flaws during the data collection procedure. During the procedure, as showed in the research summary section under A.1, A.2, A.3, and A.4, the most predominant suspect that could have created a situation where the statistical analysis may not represent any correlation, is the sample size. Although the researcher had followed the necessary steps such as stratified sampling method with the Krejcie and Morgen (1970), during the researcher's revisit and the secondary inquiry of the business owners of the tested mobile app, it has been determined that the actual conditions during the business practice have caused insignificance circumstance due to the huge user base. Therefore, the researcher suggests an alternative research approach and this research to be further studied under more controlled environment in future.

REFERENCES

- [1] Arvidsson, N., Markendahl, J., 2014. International Cashless Society Roundtable (ICSR), Stockholm.
- [2] Berry, L. L., A. E. Wall and L. P. Carbone (2006), "Service Clues and Customer Assessment of the Service Experience: Lesson From Marketing," *Academy of Management Perspective*, 20 (2), 43-57.
- [3] Bryman, A. (1988) *Quantity and Quality in Social Research*. London, Unwin Hyman.
- [4] Carton, F., Hedman, J., 2013. *Proceedings: Second International Cashless Society Roundtable (ICSR)*. Financial Services Innovation Centre.
- [5] Chase, R. B. and S. Dasu (2001), "Want to Perfect Your Company's Service? Use Behavioral Science," *Harvard Business Review*, 79 (6), 78-84.
- [6] Creswell, J.W. (2003), *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*, 2nd editions, published by Sage Publications (2003)
- [7] Dialog Internal Archives (2019) *Performance Archives 2019*. (2019). Dialog Axiata PLC.
- [8] Dialog Internal Archives (2020) *Performance Archives 2020*. (2020). Dialog Axiata PLC.
- [9] Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Jackson, P.R. (2008) *Management Research (3rd edn)*. London: Sage.
- [10] Edvardsson, B., Gustafsson, A. and Roos, I. (2005), "Service portraits in service research: a critical review", *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, Vol. 16 No. 1, pp. 107-121
- [11] Evans, D.S., Schmalensee, R., 2005. *Paying with plastic: the digital revolution in buying and borrowing*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA.
- [12] Frei, F. X. (2006), "Breaking the Trade-Off Between Efficiency and Service," *Harvard Business Review*, 84 (11), 92-103.
- [13] Hedman, J., 2012. *Proceedings First International Cashless Society Roundtable (ICSR)*. Copenhagen Finance IT Region, Copenhagen, Denmark, April 18 & 19.
- [14] Holzer, A. & Ondrus, J (2009), *Trends in Mobile Application Development: Mobile Wireless Middleware, Operating Systems and Applications-Workshops*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009.
- [15] Kaya, F. (2009). *The Credit Card Applications in Turkey*, The Association of Banks Turkey (Türkiye'de Kredi Kartı Uygulaması. Türkiye Bankalar Birliği), 263: 118-123.
- [16] Mark Saunders, Philip Lewis and Adrian Thornhill 2009, *Research Methods for Business Students*, Pearson Education Limited.
- [17] Meyer, C., and Schwager, A. (2007), "Understanding Customer Experience", *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 85 No. 2, pp. 117-127.
- [18] *Payment Journal* (2020). *Why Chinese Mobile Payment Players Are Happy with Slow U.S. Mobile Payment Adoption*. [online] *PaymentsJournal*. Available at: <https://www.paymentsjournal.com/chinese-mobile-payment-players-happy-slow-u-s-mobile-payment-adoption/> [Accessed 25 Nov. 2019].
- [19] Power, J. (2012) (n.d.). *Cultivating a developer ecosystem*. Alcatel-Lucent. Retrieved February 12, 2012, Available at: <http://www2.alcatel-lucent.com/knowledge-center/ae.php> [Accessed 27 Dec. 2019].
- [20] Pullman, M. E. and M. A. Gross (2004), "Ability of Experience Design Elements to Elicit Emotions and Loyalty Behaviors," *Decision Sciences*, 35 (3), 551-578.
- [21] Roth, R. E. (2012). *Cartographic interaction primitives: Framework and synthesis*. *The Cartographic Journal*, 49(4), 376-395.
- [22] Sara Kleinberg (2018) *Google/Heart+Mind Strategies*, 'Getting Things Done on Mobile', Feb. 2018, A18+ smartphone users, n=4,664. Data aggregated across US, UK, AU, DE and JP Available at: <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/consumer-insights/smartphone-productivity-tools/> [Accessed 27 Dec. 2019].
- [23] Schmenner, R. W. (2004), "Service Businesses and Productivity," *Decision Sciences*, 35 (3), 333- 347.

- [24] Schmenner, R. W. and M. L. Swink (1998), "On Theory in Operations Management," *Journal of Operations Management*, 17 (1), 97-113.
- [25] Solis, Brian. (2018). The Mobile Customer Journey Is The New Customer Journey; Design Accordingly. [online] Forbes.com. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/briansolis/2018/06/20/the-mobile-customer-journey-is-the-new-customer-journey-design-it/#7ef69c855a6f> [Accessed 27 Dec. 2019].
- [26] Statista (2020). Mobile app revenues 2014-2023 | Statista. [online] Statista. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/269025/worldwide-mobile-app-revenue-forecast/> [Accessed 7 Jan. 2020].
- [27] Verhoef, P. C., G. Antonides, and A. N. de Hoog (2004), "Service Encounters as a Sequence of Events: The Importance of Peak Experiences," *Journal of Service Research*, 7 (1), 53-64.
- [28] Verhoef, P. C., Lemon, K. N., Parasuraman, A., Roggeveen, A., Tsiros, M., and Schlesinger, L. A. (2009). "Customer Experience Creation: Determinants, Dynamics and Management Strategies", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 85 No. 1, pp. 31-41
- [29] W. Rodgers, S. Negash, and K. Suk, "The moderating effect of on - line experience on the antecedents and consequences of on - line satisfaction," *Psychology and Marketing*, vol. 22, pp. 313-331, 2005.
- [30] Zikmund, W.G. (2000) *Business Research Methods* (6th edn). Fort Worth, TX: Dryden Press. Economic and Social Data Service (2007) A step by step ESDS guide to: archiving and reusing data: consent issues. Available at: <http://www.esds.ac.uk/support/E8.asp>